

Valorisation of Human Organic Waste for Sustainable Domestic Biogas and Fertilizer Synthesis

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Abstract

This study proposed and discussed various “domestic” onsite sanitation (OSS) designs that incorporate anaerobic digestion (AD) process to produce biogas and organic solid fertilizer whilst treating human excreta. The prototype OSS AD Toilet was designed, developed and trialled in the field.

Prior to designing the OSS ADT facility, fresh human excreta from 10 test persons between the age range 18 – 29 years were sampled using sampling buckets and analysed to obtain data for mean faecal mass and physico-chemical composition. Median faeces generated was 250 g/cap/day wet mass and 62 g/cap/day dry mass, as well as high solid contents i.e. TS (49 g/cap/day) and VS (91% of TS i.e. 44.59 g/cap/day). Mean value for COD determined was 68 g/cap/day, while the mean nitrogen value from faeces was 1.2 g/cap/day and that of urine was 7 g/cap/day.

Residual organic fertilizer deduced was 22g/cap/day. Water boiling test showed that biogas concentration is higher in purified biogas (90 ± 1.53 %) than in raw biogas (68 ± 2.52 %). Cooking time and calorific value of biogas investigated using 1L of water was 6.54 ± 0.04 and 5.45 ± 0.02 for raw and purified gas respectively. Refrigerant reciprocating compressor reduced the biogas volume by a factor of 4.0 with an absolute pressure of 5 bars in total of approximately 12 minutes.

This study explored that OSS ADTS is an innovative and most preferable treatment approach for human waste management in rural and peri-urban areas in Papua New Guinea and can be replicated in other places with similar setting and conditions, fostering benefits in the light of Sustainable Development.

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List of Abbreviations

AD	anaerobic digestion
ADT	anaerobic digester toilet
ADTS	anaerobic digester toilet system
BMP	bio-chemical methane potential
CO ₂	carbon dioxide
dm ³	cubic decimetres (litres)
E _{BG}	biogas energy content
EU	European Union
GHG	greenhouse gas
HOW	human organic waste
kg	kilograms
kJ	kilojoules
km	kilometres
kWh	kilowatt hours
LPG	liquified petrol gas
m	meters
m _{BG}	biogas mass
m _{HOW}	human organic waste mass
m _{VS}	volatile solids mass
MSW	municipal solid waste
m ³	cubic meters
N	nitrogen
OFMSW	organic fraction of municipal solid waste
OLR	organic loading rate
OM	costs for operation and maintenance
OSS	onsite sanitation
OW	organic waste
RE	renewable energy

RT	hydraulic retention time
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TS	total solids
V_{BG}	biogas volumes
V_D	digester volume
V_{OW}	volumes of solid organic waste
V_w	water volumes
vol.	volume
VS	volatile solids
VS_{TS}	relative volatile solids content
WHO	world health organization
$^{\circ}C$	degrees Celsius

1.0 BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE OF THE RESEARCH

Approximately 2.6 billion people globally lack access to proper sanitation, referred to as hygienic separation of human excreta i.e. human faeces and urine from human contact (WHO/UNICEF, 2012). Diseases that associates with inadequate sanitation particularly faecal-oral diseases such as diarrhea, dysentery, typhoid etc. correlates to poverty and makes up 10% of the total global disease burden (Pruss-Ustun et al., 2008). According to a report by WHO/UNICEF (2012), in 2010 59% of sanitation facilities in South Asia and 72% in Sub-Saharan Africa countries were categorized as “unimproved”. Onsite sanitation (OSS) facilities are the conventional and predominantly used in urban populations of developing countries for human excreta disposal; for instance, 85% of inhabitants in urban areas of Tanzania and Ghana uses OSS facilities and 98% of urban dwellers in the Philippines resort to OSS facilities (Montangero and Strauss, 2004). However, the notable limitation is lack of financial incentives or inadequate treatment facilities when need of emptying arises, resulting often in filled pits that are usually covered and new ones dug, or often left desolate or if emptied, sludge is discharged openly into the environment degrading soil and aquifer systems (Ingallinella et al., 2002). Accordingly, research and development to further improve current OSS systems is crucial, particularly development of OSS facilities that treat human waste at, or near its source.

Special regard is accorded to this problem as demonstrated by accelerated interest in increasing studies in OSS technology, with Bill Gates Foundation (BGF) taking the forefront in funding 16 “Reinvent the Toilet Challenge” (RTTC) research and development projects globally since 2011, for instance, awarding Chinese research institutes US\$5 million for rigorous studies and development of new OSS technologies (Global Development Program, 2014).

Advances are also made towards creating added value of human excreta as an incentive to alter the global perspectives accordingly to encourage proper management. Human excreta is referred to as human organic waste (HOW) throughout discussions in this paper. Advantage for energy recovery by utilizing waste as a resource is promising as wastes are omnipresent and in abundance. Waste-to-energy is the major shift in global perspective that is acquiring immense interests and fascination, as waste generation continues to escalate and the global demand for energy continues to increase. Recent studies have shown that HOW has a huge potential to be an alternate source of

energy, as 66 – 70% of methane gas can be derived (Arthur and Brew-Hammond, 2010). Methane gas is an alternative source of renewable household energy.

Although human waste has huge energy potential which can be tapped into, limitations are inherent. Social and cultural issues, economic issues and the regulations and management policies determine the fate of the application and effectiveness of this concept, Buxton and Reed (2010). Past studies have been conducted on the different technologies that can be used to exploit human waste to energy; however, most of these technologies are complex, and expensive to operate and maintain (Luostarinen et al., 2011). Until in recent decade, the diffusion of bio-digester system is promulgated, and governmental and non-governmental organisations are now actively collaborating in awarding subsidies and incentives, and research and development of such systems Bond & Templeton (2011). Numerous countries in Africa and Asia, including Kenya, Tanzania Rwanda, India, Bangladesh, Nepal, China, Vietnam, and Cambodia are vigorously promoting biogas technology through massive campaigns (Kossmann, et al., 1988).

This research project is relevant to slums, peri-urban and rural areas simply because of lack of proper sanitation and the need to manage HOW, by reducing health and environmental impacts, simultaneously creating economic returns in terms of energy generation and fertilizer production. The novel design is suitable at places where there is no centralized wastewater treatment plant and or municipal sewage treatment system.

1.1 Problem statement

Lack of proper urban planning, rapid urbanization, and economic boom in the recent decades has triggered rapid growth in slums and peri-urban areas on the outskirts of the towns and cities around Papua New Guinea (PNG). These marginalized populations are denied the right to proper health, sanitation, and energy (World Vision Australia: Papua New Guinea Profile, 2013). Hossain and Moniruzzaman (2010) pointed out that in most developing countries cesspits and latrines are common avenues where human wastes are disposed. It is also not uncommon that HOW is dumped untreated in the open, in waterways or on marginal land, which is inaesthetic (Regattieri et al., 2016). This can result in environmental pollution and severe health risks, further exacerbating the living conditions, for instance, faecal-oral and diarrhoea. Communicable diseases such as these

results in mortality and morbidity, where their transmissions are influenced by hygienic behaviours (Regattieri et al., 2018). According to World Health Organization (WHO) there are 173 deaths per 1000 due to diarrheal diseases in PNG. Onsite treatment of human organic waste is therefore imperative, due to its pathogenic nature and environmental, social and safety reasons.

1.2 Relevance of the study

This study aims at contributing to organic waste (OW) management by designing a cheap and user-friendly onsite sanitation (OSS) anaerobic digester toilet system (ADTS) for domestic biogas production from HOW using basic and available materials. Existing materials such as tanks and pipes can be reused or recycled to produce this system. ADTS will essentially consist of a toilet connected to simple digesters which operate under anaerobic conditions to produce biogas. It will be simple, cheap and require minimal maintenance, which are primary importance even if the system efficiency is low. Alternative options to purify and conveniently store biogas will be explored. In parallel, residual solid matter can be considered as fertilizer for agricultural use (Regattieri et al., 2016). This technological solution will not only tackle sanitary issues but it will simultaneously generate useful secondary energy source, reduces environmental pollution, and lessens the dependency on fossil fuels (Andriani et al., 2015; Regattieri et al., 2016).

1.3 Objectives

- i. Design and fabricate an eco-friendly and environmentally friendly domestic OSS ADT system suitable to developing countries
- ii. Create added value to human organic waste in terms of biogas and fertiliser synthesis
- iii. Establish affordable purification, compression and storage alternative for biogas

1.4 Scope of the study

Scope of the study to achieve the mentioned objectives encompass:

1. Formulate survey questionnaires to explore locals' perspectives on HOW management, biogas as alternate energy sources and OSS ADT technology for HOW volarisation.
2. Design and fabricate anaerobic digester toilet (ADT) using affordable and accessible materials.
3. Analysis and determination of physio-chemical characteristics of human waste, as well as the operational parameters of anaerobic digester (AD) system.
4. Conduct biomethane potential (BMP) test for human organic waste as the feedstock.
5. Integrating co-digestion to increase biogas and fertilizer production.
6. Utilize affordable and or accessible waste materials to develop and establish cost-effective biogas purification, compression and storage mechanism.

2.0 PRELIMINARY LITERATURE REVIEW

Proper management of HOW is of paramount importance to mitigate its associated impacts on the human health and environment especially in developing countries. Unimproved sanitation facilities and faecal sludge management have caused extensive harm to the human population and the natural ecosystems (Ingallinella et al., 2002; Andriani et al, 2015). These controversial issues have sparked interest in research and development of on-site sanitation (OSS) systems that focus on treating HOW directly at or close to its source with no need for further transport. OSS technologies are amongst the common and most effective approach of treating HOW in developing countries, as these facilities seeks to provide an affordable and hygienic mode of disposing HOW by applying treatment at source (Rose et al, 2015). However, the notable limitation is lack of financial incentives or inadequate treatment facilities when need of emptying arises, resulting often in filled pits that are usually covered and new ones dug, or often left desolate or if emptied, sludge is discharged openly into the environment degrading soil and aquifer systems (Ingallinella et al., 2002). Accordingly, research and development to further improve current OSS systems is crucial, particularly development of OSS facilities that treat HOW at, or near its source.

2.1 Onsite sanitation facilities in developing countries

Inadequate or unimproved existing OSS facilities in many developing countries often results from poor design, construction, and maintenance. This propels research and development to determine appropriate treatment at source and or resource recovery approach for HOW specific to a developing country context. This approach has been globally accelerated by the Bill and Melinda Gates foundation (BMGF) with the challenge presented to researchers to “Reinvent the Toilet” (Global Development Program, 2013).

Recent studies have advanced to look at compatible and cost-effective designs that suits preferred settings. Pharmaceuticals Century Limited in India introduced an anaerobic biodigester system that uses the plug-flow digester principle as show in Figure 1. The technology is now commercialized and is installed around most towns and outskirts of major cities in India. However,

a constant water supply is necessary for the system to operate and so is deemed unsuitable for areas deprived of proper and/ or constant water supply.

Figure 1: Bio toilet with digester (Courtesy: Century Pharmaceuticals Limited)

safe to dispose of, and has been specifically designed as a solution to PNG's high water table environments. Despite the many advantages associated with it, such as portability, durability, prevention of aquifer pollution, etc., it is expensive and does not give an economic return. In addition, it does not solve the associated environmental problems holistically; meaning carbon dioxide and methane gases are being emitted to the atmosphere, and so continues to contribute to the ever-increasing global warming.

Figure 2: SAGO dry toilet (Courtesy of SAGO)

A Dry Toilet technology (Figure 2) developed by SAGO, a not-for-profit, non-government organisation that has been working in Papua New Guinea (PNG) addresses the need of water. In its attempt to strengthen lives of people in PNG by improving water, sanitation and hygiene standards at a community level, SAGO's Dry Toilet technology introduced is an above ground, waterless latrine that dries out waste, making a sand-like output that is

The most recent technological concept that deals with HOW management is proposed by Regattieri (2018). His concept of waterless biodigester toilet design for domestic biogas production and consumption (Figure 3) was remarkable as it captures most features of an improved OSS facility lacked by previous OSS systems. Dry anaerobic digestion mostly consists of more than 15% w/w of TS, and is advantageous due to less water required, minimal reactor volume and high biogas

productivity than wet digestion. Nonetheless, Zeshan & Tojo (2012) argued that the main limitations to dry digestion is accumulation of ammonia due to improper C:N ratio from HOW, which Rose et al., stated that is mainly derived from urine (i.e. 0.8:1), while the optimal C:N ratio

Figure 3: Design of the anaerobic digester toilet (Regattieri, 2018)

is 20:1 – 30:1 (Li et al., 2011; Wang. *et.al*, 2014; Paritosh et al., 2017; Feathers, 2021). Urine produce ammonia, which is toxic to methane producing bacteria (Luostarinen et al., 2011) and so has to be separated from source prior to entering the digester(s).

As well as that, the sustainability aspect of the technology was not sufficiently considered, in terms of appropriate mechanisms through which slurry, particularly the solid residues of undigested waste can be removed from the

anaerobic digester. Further to that, the biogas that is produced is a mixture of gases which requires a purification unit to improve the methane quality, thereby increasing the calorific content. Past studies in this field have significantly overlooked this area, which off course is imperative for quality domestic biogas production and consumption purposes. However, to design and develop a suitable OSS technological solution to this problem, prior knowledge of HOW that enters the treatment facility is pivotal.

2.2 Human waste generation and characterization

Information pertaining to conventional sanitary sewage is available (Tchobanoglous et al., 2003; Henze et al., 2001;), unfortunately the materials studied have different compositions as compared to fresh faeces and urine which has substantially less water or grey water added as they are yet to undergo degradation processes. In addition, rate of HOW generation and its chemical composition in terms of faeces and urine as outlined in Table 1, 2 & 3 are key factors to be understood prior to designing and developing suitable OSS technologies.

2.2.1 Human waste generation rate

Rose et al., (2015) pointed out that diet, total food intake, and body weight are major factors that lead to variation in faecal generation rate, while fibre intake is the main factor affecting faecal mass. Additionally, as shown in Table 1 urine and sanitary items such as toilet papers amalgamate to give the total rate of waste generation which slightly differs amongst male and female.

Table 1: Daily wet and dry mass of human faeces produced from low and high income (Rose et al., 2015)

	Wet weight	Wet weight	Dry weight	Dry weight
	(g/cap/day)	(g/cap/day)	(g/cap/day)	(g/cap/day)
	High income	Low income	High income	Low income
Maximum	796	520	081	062
Minimum	051	075	012	018
Median	126	250	028	038
n	095	017	057	008
Skewness	4.18	0.60	2.38	0.10
Std. error of skewness	0.25	0.55	0.33	0.75
Mean	149	243	030	039
St dev	95.0	130	11.7	14.1

The dietary intake of non-degradable fibre known as cellulose is the predominant factor leading to variation in key parameters in faeces, hence, influencing the stool frequency and generation rate, TS, fat, protein, and the calorific (energy) value of faeces.

Table 2: Generation rate of human organic waste in waste streams with additional inputs (Rose et al., 2015)

Component of solids fraction	Generation rate (g/cap/day)	Component of liquid fraction (L/cap/day)	Generation rate
Stool mean (range)	32 (4–102)	Stool water mean (range)	0.101 (0.053–0.265)

Urine	61 (50–75)	Urine median (range)	1.42 (0.8–2.45)
Toilet paper use average	11.68–19.4	Anal cleansing L/wash	0.35–3
Toilet paper use men	6–10.3	Pour flush toilet water L/flush	1–3
Toilet paper use women	17.9–36		
Menstrual pads and flow	34		

2.2.2 Human waste composition

An extensive review on characterization of human faeces and urine by Rose et al., (2015) basing on large established database of values from studies globally, as summarized in Table 3 provides a key criteria and figures that will assist to advance research and development to upgrade existing OSS facilities or design and develop new OSS technologies.

Table 3: Human faeces and urine characteristics summary provided for on-site sanitation design criteria

Key design criteria	Median value
<i>Faeces</i>	1.1
Stool frequency (motions/24 hr)	
Faecal wet weight (g/cap/day)	128
Faecal dry weight (g/cap/day)	29
Total solids (%)	25
VS (% of TS)	89
COD (g/cap/day)	71
Nitrogen (g/cap/day)	1.8
Protein (g/cap/day)	6.3
Lipids (g/cap/day)	4.1
Carbohydrate (g/cap/day)	9
Fibre (g/cap/day)	6
Calorific value (kcal/cap/day)	132

pH	6.6
<i>Urine</i>	
Urine wet weight (L/cap/day)	1.4
Urine dry weight (g/cap/day)	59
Urination frequency (urinations/24 hr)	6
Nitrogen (g/cap/day)	11
Calorific value (kcal/cap/day)	1701
pH	6.2

2.2.3 Organic fraction of human waste

Faeces

Human faeces compose a median value of 75% water content, with 25% of the remaining weight of faeces being the solid component, wherein between 84% and 93% of the solid fraction being the organic material (Feachem et al., 1978; Nwaneri et al., 2008; Bai and Wang, 2011). The total organic solid fraction consists of: bacterial biomass (25–54%) (Guyton and Hall, 2000; Stephen and Cummings, 1980), protein in nitrogen form (2–25%, with bacterial biomass being 50% protein) (Volk and Rummel, 1987; Canfield et al., 1963), carbohydrate or cellulose (25%) (Volk and Rummel, 1987), and 2–15% being undigested lipids (Chen et al., 1998; Kien et al., 1981; Wierdsma et al., 2011). The stated figures and percentage compositions is directly proportional to diets and the relative biological availability (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Daily weights per capita of organic fractions in human faeces (Rose et al., 2015).

Majority of dried solids comprises of organic fraction of HOW. Snyder et al. (1975) stated that median carbon content of faeces is 7 g/cap/day, or range between 44% and 55% of dried solids argued Feachem et al. (1978) and Strauss (1985). Volatile solids (VS) comprise 92% of the total solids (TS) fraction of faeces (Fry and Merrill, 1973). Chemical means can be used to measure bulk organic content of faeces with special regard to biological oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD).

Urine

Urine is secreted by kidneys and exits the body through urethral discharge, with water content amount to between 91– 96% (Heinonen-Tanski et al., 2007; Drangert, 1998; Hoglund et al., 2000;) with the rest being urea, inorganic salts, salts of organic ammonium, and organic compounds (Putnam, 1971). Between 65 – 85% of urine dry solids comprise of organic matter (Strauss, 1985), with 75 – 85% of TS being volatile solids (House, 1981; Fry and Merrill, 1973). Urea, produced via metabolism of protein constitute 50% of total organic solids, and is the most predominant constituent. Elemental composition of dry urine solids showed 14–18% nitrogen, 13% carbon, 3.7% phosphorus, and 3.7% potassium (Strauss, 1985). Considering compositions of faeces and urine, urine has the largest proportion of N (90%), K (50–80%) and P (50–65%) excreted from the body (Heinonen-Tanski and van Wijk-Sijbesma, 2005). Nitrogen concentration variations in urine is predominantly influenced by dietary protein intake.

With in-depth knowledge on generation rate and composition of human organic waste, one can now be able to make an informed decision on preferable treatment pathways (Table 4) for human organic waste, as well as design and develop appropriate OSS technology for its treatment at given locality.

2.3 Biological processes for human waste treatment

Biological processes specifically anaerobic process is preferable for treating human faeces as it has very high moisture content (>75%), which results in water logging, a natural process that encouraging anaerobic conditions to develop (Tiquia et al., 1996). Feasibility of such potential hinge on type and design of anaerobic digester, hydraulic retention time (HRT), and biodegradability of material (Mang and Li, 2010). For example, fibre content of faeces is a key variable which differs widely (Table 4); particularly diets high in fibre (such as diets consumed mostly in developing countries). This corresponds to reduced COD conversions due to relatively lower decomposition rate of fibrous material.

Table 4: Classifications of treatment pathways in wastewater treatment

Process type	Examples	Resource recovery
Biological	Anaerobic digestion	Biogas
	Wet and dry composting	Compost fertilizer
	UASB	Biofuel production
	Decoupled HRT and SRT	Digestate/Biosolids/liquid fraction
Thermal processes	Incineration	Energy/Ash
	Pyrolysis/gasification	Energy/Char
Separation	Membrane pervaporation	Pyrolysis
	Biofiltration	Pathogen free water
Chemical processes	Ammonia disinfection	NPK irrigation water/fertilizer
	Electrochemical disinfection	Pathogen free products

Ammonia stripping

Fertilizer

Struvite

Phosphorus

On a broader context, this study looks at treating faeces and urine as a fresh waste stream at the source of generation, with special regard to generation, composition, and associated variations concerning these factors in order to ascertain how this may impact the proposed OSS technology.

2.3.1 Anaerobic digestion process

Anaerobic digestion is a series of biological processes in which different species of bacteria break down organic matter, in the absence of oxygen (Li et al., 2011). The sequential biochemical processes occur in four distinct phases (Figure 4), i.e. hydrolysis, acidogenesis, acetogenesis and methanogenesis (Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011, Paritosh et al., 2017, Baltrėnas and Baltrėnaitė, 2018).

Figure 5: Phases in anaerobic digestion

Stage 1: Hydrolysis – decomposition of complex organic molecules into simpler organic molecules i.e. short-chain sugars, peptides and amino acids via reaction with water (Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011; Paritosh et al., 2017).

Stage 2: Acidogenesis – conversion of simple organic molecules into fatty acids (simple carboxylic acids), by acidogenes and acetogens to produce ketones (glycerol, acetone – Reaction 2), and alcohols (ethanol, methanol – Reaction 3).

Stage 3 Acetogenesis – conversion of fatty acids into acetate where carbon dioxide, as well as hydrogen is formed, which are necessary precursors for the final phase of the digestion process to take place, as shown in reactions 4-7:

Stage 4 Methanogenesis – final phase of AD where volatile fatty acids, hydrogen gas (H_2), CO_2 , and water (H_2O) are converted to methane. However, several reactions occur simultaneously using the intermediate products from the other phases, with the main product being methane, as illustrated in reactions 8-13:

As shown by multiple reaction pathways (reaction 8 – 13), methane is the predominant product of the chemical processes and constitute 50 – 75% (vol.) of biogas yield, followed by carbon dioxide with 25 to 55 % (vol.), respectively, with remaining fractions of gas mixture being nitrogen, ammonia, hydrogen sulphides and water vapor beside methane and carbon dioxide (Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011; Surendra et al., 2014).

2.3.2 Factors affecting anaerobic digestion processes

Biological processes are predominantly impacted to the greatest extent by factors like loading of solids, calorific content, concentration of fat and protein in the faeces and the increased urea concentrations in urine. The overall AD process is classified (Table 5) with respect to how the biogas production unit operates.

Table 5: Anaerobic digestion process classifications

Substrate feeding continuity	Operating temp.	Content of solids
Batch	Psychrophilic	Wet digestion
Semi-continuous	Mesophilic	Dry digestion
Continuous	Thermophilic	

Since series of bio-chemical reactions occur simultaneously during the anaerobic digestion process involving various kinds of microorganisms, final biogas yields highly depend essential key process parameters and operating conditions such as; temperature, pH, substrate composition, and substrate retention time, (Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011; Li et al., 2011; Paritosh et al., 2017), which in turn determines the intermediate activity and metabolism of bacteria to produce biogas.

An essential and vital tool that indicates the potential rate and extent to which an organic matter can be converted to methane is the so-called bio-chemical methane potential (BMP) (Alibardi and Cossu, 2015; Nallathambi Gunaseelan, 1997; Paritosh et al., 2017). The following discusses operational parameters that determine the efficacy of the anaerobic decomposition processes.

Substrate

The organic material that undergoes AD processes is commonly referred to as feedstock, as it is fed into the digester. However, ‘substrate’ is commonly used both in the literature and in this report instead of ‘feedstock’ when discussing material properties that are critical for the formation of biogas and methane, respectively. Essentially all biomass can be considered as substrate for biogas production due to their carbohydrates, fats and proteins contents (Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011).

However, not all substrate fed into the digester undergo bacterial decomposition to produce methane due to either inhibition arising from toxic conditions or resistance of long chain carbohydrates like cellulose to degrade (Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011). The fraction of organic material from the feedstock that theoretically undergo bacterial decomposition is known as volatile solids (VS).

For different feedstocks, the volume of biogas produced is proportional to the quantity of material in the digester that is subject to bacterial degradation. Different types of organic materials (Table 6) are suitable as feedstocks for digestion, for example food waste from households, restaurants and shops, sewage sludge, animal manure, grey water from the food industry and various plant materials (Gabriela, 2010). Substrate is fed into the digester either through batch, continuous flow or semi-continuous (Table 5). Unlike batch process, semi-continuous and continuous process are preferred due to higher production stability, predictability, and biogas yields (Huber, 2019). Further to that, the process is self-regulatory as process residue, i.e. a portion of the digestate remained at the end of the cycle to replenish microorganisms in the digester which initiate commencement of the AD process with the new material fed once again (Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011; Li et al., 2011; Obiukwu and Nwafor, 2016; Talia, 2018).

Table 6: Comparison of raw material and yielded biogas (Andriani, et al., 2015)

Source	Waste amount/day/Kg	% Water	Dry matter	Biogas m ³ /Kg dry waste
Buffalo	20 – 30 (28)	83	20	0.023 – 0.040
Cow	20 – 30 (28)	80	20	0.023 – 0.040
Pig	3.00 – 4.00 (3.40)	67	9	0.04 – 0.059
Roaster/Hen	0.15 – 0.20 (0.18)	72	28	0.065 – 0.116
Human	0.10 – 0.40 (0.15)	77	23	0.02 – 0.028

Temperature

Recommended temperature for optimal biogas production is in the mesophilic range i.e. between 20 - 39 °C; below 10 °C or above 65 °C results in very slow biodegradation process due to survival of very few strains of bacteria (Kristoferson & Bokalders, 1986; Depledge, D., 1997).

pH

pH simply put is a major indicator of the anaerobic digester performance. Naturally occurring set of complex buffers control pH within the digester, with organic acid-ammonia and bicarbonate being the most essential buffers. The optimal pH range for AD is neutral to slightly basic i.e. pH 6.6 to 7.6.

Carbon: Nitrogen ratio

The optimal C:N ratios of an anaerobic system suggested by a number of researchers is said to be between 20:1 – 30:1 (Li et al., 2011; Wang. *et.al*, 2014; Paritosh et al., 2017; Feathers, 2021); which is unlikely either in faeces (8:1), in urine (0.8:1) or as a combined (faecal + urine) waste stream (2.3:1). The increase of C:N ratios maximise toxic effects of ammonia and reduced methane

potentials (Wang. *et.al*, 2014), whereas a lack of nitrogen impedes formation of protein which is essential for metabolic activity of microorganisms (Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011; Paritosh et al., 2017). Hence, it is imperative to maintain tolerable C:N ratio for optimal system performance. However, co-digestion essentially with the use of other organic waste substrates can rectify imbalances in the macronutrient composition and could be a simple corrective action to increasing the viability of biological systems.

Total solid content

The total solid content of a substrate is the amount of dry matter present in the material that is measured as the dry weight. Digestibility of the feedstock depends to a larger extent on the total solid (TS) content and the volatile solid (VS). TS content in the range 15 to 20 % (Shi et al., 2013; Talia, 2018) and water content greater than 75% (Tiquia et al., 1996; Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011) are strong indicators for wet digestion application when using human organic waste resources as a substrate/feedstock for biogas production (Talia, 2018). The fraction of organic material from the feedstock that theoretically undergo bacterial decomposition is known as volatile solids (VS). With known TS and VS values, the amount of biogas producible can be theoretically determined. Wet digestion accounts for better mixing of substrate to enhance substrate properties for stable rate of biogas production and off course smooth substrate transfer for treatment etc. (Li et al., 2011; Deublein and Steinhauser, 2011; Talia, 2018). A comparison of biogas production performance between wet and dry digestion shows improved economic and energetic features with wet digestion in terms of large-scale and commercial production units (Angelonidi and Smith, 2015; Li et al., 2011; Talia, 2018). An illustration of a design for small-scale digesters that uses wet digestion process for decomposition of manure as main feedstock is shown in Figure. 6.

Figure 6: Plug flow digester

Organic loading rate

The organic loading rate (OLR) refers to the rate at which feedstock in terms of VS is added to the digester and whereby biogas production rate is proportional to OLR (Paritosh et al., 2017). Excess increase in OLR can overloading the digester due to higher concentrations of volatile fatty acids which cause pH of system to reduce, hence, inhibiting bio-chemical processes (Xu et al., 2018). Application of higher OLR in advanced technologies requires continuous stirring mechanisms. However, for small-scale digesters such as those predominant in most developing countries for instance, Sub-Sahara African countries, as well as India, OLR of around 2 kg_{VS} per m³ digester volume per day (Vögeli et al. 2014) is sufficient and replace the need for a stirring device in biogas production unit.

Ammonia

Protein degradation and urea reduction consequently produce ammonia gas (NH₃) and its relative ammonium ion (NH₄⁺). NH₃ whose toxicity is dependent on pH is predominant in alkaline condition and is much more toxic than NH₄⁺. In most cases ammonia is tolerable to levels as high as 6,000 mg/l given the microorganisms are able to adapt in digesters, except for highly nitrogenous feedstock such as poultry manure.

Sulphate and sulphide

Sulphate (SO_4^-) is non-toxic, but its reduced form sulphide (S^{-2}) is more toxic to the anaerobic processes and possess similar toxic properties as NH_3 . S^{-2} exists in a gaseous form just like ammonia and the toxicity of S^{-2} is dependent on digester pH.

2.4 Biogas technology

Biogas is the by-product of anaerobic digestion; a biological process that breaks down organic materials in an oxygen-free environment. To produce biogas, feedstocks are supplied into tightly sealed tank known as digester, where chemical decomposition occurs to convert the energy stored in biomass feedstock into biogas. The quantity and quality of biogas produced is influenced by essential operational parameters (*as discussed in Section 2.3.2*), which includes the temperature, pH, feedstock composition, feedstock loading rate, digester design, and retention time.

Studies done by Onojo et al. (2013) on estimation of the electric power potential of human waste validate human waste as a source of biogas - an alternate renewable energy source. Prominent advantage for HW as a resource for biogas production is lack of need for starter (microorganism), as it is derived from the anaerobic decomposition in the gastrointestinal tract, which contain high faecal anaerobic bacteria (Andriani et al, 2015). Animal waste can be supplemented to HW due to their higher fibre contents to enhance biogas production.

Since biogas technology is being recognised amongst the most energy-efficient and environmentally friendly technologies for bioenergy production (Andriani et al., 2015), utilization of HW via anaerobic digestion as a means of treatment whilst simultaneously producing biogas can minimize the associated environmental and health implications. This is essentially true for low-income countries due to lack of “improved” health and sanitary facilities.

Figure 7 shows three predominant forms of conventional domestic digesters used in the developing countries i.e., the fixed-dome digester or Chinese digester, the plug flow digester (also called sausage-bag or tubular/plastic digester), and the floating drum digester (also called telescopic digester or Hindu digester). Though the digester designs and biogas collection approach differ significantly, the principle behind the digestion process is the same, as well as the by-products obtained. Domestic digesters are normally smaller than industrial digesters; and they are either

constructed onsite or prefabricated with different materials, such as concrete, brick, and plastics (Bond & Templeton, 2011).

Figure 7: Digester types: (a) plug flow digester (b) fixed-dome digester (c) floating drum digester (Marchaim, 1996)

Mang and Li, (2010) eloquently pointed that practical delivery and success of potential biogas production depends largely on digester type and design, retention time, and biodegradability of feedstock such that actual conversion of the available organic matter in biomass to biogas is expected to range between 40% and 90%.

2.4.1 General features of biogas

Biogas is a colourless flammable gas produced via anaerobic digestion. It mainly consists of methane, carbon dioxide and several impurities (Table 8), and becomes flammable when the methane content is at least 45%. Biogas is an emerging alternate renewable source of energy which is an excellent replacement of fossil fuels, and can be used to produce heat, light and electricity (Table 9)

Composition, energy content, density and molar mass of biogas are listed in Table 7. The composition of gas depends on the source of feedstock and the management of the digestion process.

Table 7: General features of biogas [Deublein & Steihauser, 2008]

Composition	55-70% methane (CH₄) 30-45% carbon dioxide (CO₂) Traces of other gases
Normal density	1.2 kg m ⁻³
Molar Mass	16.043 kgkmol ⁻¹
Energy content	6.0-6.5 kWh m ⁻³
Ignition temperature	650-750 °C
Explosion limits	6-12% biogas in air
Fuel equivalent	0.60-0.65L oil m ⁻³ biogas
Critical pressure	75-89 bar
Critical temperature	-82.5 °C
Smell	Rotten eggs

Table 8: Typical components and impurities in biogas [Deublein & Steihauser, 2008]

Component	Content*	Effect
CO ₂	25-50	-Lowers the calorific value -Causes corrosion (carbonic acid); if the gas is wet.
H ₂ S	0-0.5	-Corrosive effect on equipment and piping systems (stress corrosion) -SO ₂ emissions after burners or H ₂ S emissions
NH ₃	0-0.5	-NO _x emissions after burners
Water vapour	1-5	-Causes corrosion of equipment and piping system. -Condensates damage instruments and plants.
N ₂	0-5	-Lowers the calorific value.

* - % by volume

Table 9: Biogas usability and equivalent (Andriani, et al., 2015)

Application	1 m³ biogas equivalent
Lighting	equal to 60 -100 watt bulb for 6 hours
Cooking	can cook 3 meals for a family of 5 - 6
Fuel	replacement 0.7 kg of petroleum
Shaft power	can run a one horse power motor for 2 hours
Electricity generation	can generate 1.25 kilowatt hours of electricity

2.5 Residual organic fertiliser generation

Urine

Urine has high potential to be considered as supplementary fertilizer (AdeOluwa and Cofie, 2012; Palmquist and Jonsson, 2004; Karak and Bhattacharyya, 2011), due to its rich nutrients content Rose et al (2015) (Table 3). Further studies showed that few intestinal microorganisms are also present in urine, but are of low health risk to human health when compared to faeces. On the contrary, Feachem et al., (1978) and Heinonen-Tanski and van Wijk-Sijbesma, (2005) revealed that some pathogenic microorganisms from human such as *Salmonella typhi*, *Salmonella paratyphi*, *Leptospira interrogans* and *Schistosoma haematobium*, and helminth eggs are likely to be contained in urine. Hence, treatment and recovery of essential nutrients from urine such as nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium fertilizer are a necessity. However, the processes are costly and suitable only for industrial applications.

With the proposed ADT technology (Figure 20 & 21), since faeces and urine will be allowed to pass through a single waste stream at the source, generation of fertilizer in this study will focus more on the faecal sludge that exits the system.

Faeces

Faecal sludge can also be used as manure or as soil amendments for organic farming. With faecal composition given in Section 2.2.2 and faecal characterization values obtained from Table 3, the

total indigestible fraction of the TS content predominantly comes from carbohydrate or cellulose i.e. 25% of organic solids (Volk and Rummel, 1987), and undigested lipids i.e. 2–15% of organic solids (Chen et al., 1998; Kien et al., 1981; Wierdsma et al., 2011). The quantity of residual organic fertilizer increases as the ADTS user population increases.

Table 10: Residual solid fertilizer generation rate and quantity projection

Population	Faeces Weight (g)	TS (g)	VS (<i>Digestible</i>) (g)	Indigestible solids (in grams) after retention time (days)					
				1 day	10	20	30	60	90 days
1	250	68	61	22	223	446	668	1337	2005
2	500	135	123	45	446	891	1337	2673	4010
3	750	203	184	67	668	1337	2005	4010	6014
4	1000	270	246	89	891	1782	2673	5346	8019
5	1250	338	307	111	1114	2228	3341	6683	10024
6	1500	405	369	134	1337	2673	4010	8019	12029
7	1750	473	430	156	1559	3119	4678	9356	14033
8	2000	540	491	178	1782	3564	5346	10692	16038
9	2250	608	553	200	2005	4010	6014	12029	18043
10	2500	675	614	223	2228	4455	6683	13365	20048
50	12500	3375	3071	1114	11138	22275	33413	66825	100238
100	25000	6750	6143	2228	22275	44550	66825	133650	200475
200	50000	13500	12285	4455	44550	89100	133650	267300	400950
500	125000	33750	30713	11138	111375	222750	334125	668250	1002375
1000	250000	67500	61425	22275	222750	445500	668250	1336500	2004750

The mass of residual sludge stated in Table 10 specifically relates to the amount of solid matter obtained after treatment i.e. separation of liquid from solid using geobag, as well as the subsequent composting process.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Prior to summarizing the Thesis, the research work was divided into two main segments, where eight weeks was allocated for conducting lab tests and field work in the research area. Site visit to an OSS facility (waterless dry toilet) (Figure 2) installed at Sipaia, a village on the shoreline of Morobe Patrol Coast served to gain insight into the challenges associated with current system, and the need to improve and hopefully design and create an OSS technology that not only manage human wastes but creates value from the by-products. During the preparation phase, literature review and data mining served to provide necessary information and relevant knowledge relative to OSS facilities in developing countries, generation rate and composition of human excreta resources as a feedstock for biogas production in order to achieve the stated objectives. These objectives were formulated to achieve easy application and replicability in other similar settings. Hence, chosen method is thoroughly discussed in the Results and Discussion chapter.

3.1 Motivation and commencement of the investigation

Motivated by the aim to replicate the research findings of this Thesis work in similar settings as part of improving OSS technology and renewable energy sources, a reference point had to be identified. Collaborating with a church community as a research site was motivated by the possibility to involve local community members to promote concept awareness in new fields of applied approaches to human waste management via OSS facility, hence, alternative energy source seemed promising. Prior to the field study, a dialogue was established with one of the biggest churches in Speedway village, *Baptist Pentecostal Church*, which had more than 150 church members (including children). The head pastor of the church ministry was keen in project cooperation after a brief awareness of the study concept.

3.2 Quantitative assessment

3.2.1 Analytical methods

Figure 8: HACH Sension multi-parameter pH & conductivity meter

Operating parameters i.e. the physio-chemical parameters such as TS, VS, TN, , and total COD were determined using Standard Methods (Greenberg *et al.*, 1992). pH, temperature and COD were measured with a HACH Sension digital multi-parameter pH & conductivity meter (Figure 8). Total solids (TS) was determined by incubating sample at 104 °C until no further weight change was evident, and volatile solids (VS) was measured by the weight loss on ignition of the dried sample at 550 °C. The total gas production was measured via the liquid replacement method (LRM) method at an interval of 24 h. The pH, VS reduction, and COD reduction was measured every 7 days throughout the experiment. Each experiment was conducted within mesophilic range i.e. between $35 \pm 3^\circ \text{C}$ for 21 days.

3.2.2 Biogas yield achievable

Achievable biogas volumes are estimated based on BMP and the absolute quantities of human organic waste resources that is considered as feedstock for the AD process of the OSS facility at Speedway. The approach taken to assess the technical biogas potential of available quantities of human organic waste is illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Approach for assessing the technical potential

3.3 Study approach

The prototype of the ADT system was fabricated at the civil engineering workshop (CEW) and installed at a church community at Speedway village on the outskirts of Lae, the industrial hub of Papua New Guinea. Laboratory trials and simulations were conducted in the Environmental Laboratory (at the Civil Engineering Department) on human organic waste as the substrate to determine bio-methane potential (BMP), an important tool that determines if an organic material can degrade to produce methane.

Questionnaires and surveys were used to collect views from the participants and interested individuals as well as responsible authorities on current OSS facilities and the need for improvements.

3.3.1 Bio-methane potential test

The objective is to perform tests to provide insight into the proposed ADT system. Analysing BMP of a substrate in a laboratory when digested under anaerobic conditions is a standardized and commonly acknowledged way of determining a substrate's potential for methane formation (Holliger et al., 2016; Schievano et al., 2008). The BMP test procedure has three main components: (1) sample preparation, (2) test start up and operation, (3) data analysis and reporting.

Figure 10: Flow diagram for BMP procedure

Liquid replacement method (LRM) (Figure 11) is a suitable alternative to gas chromatogram (GC), an appropriate instrument for measuring CH_4 in biogas (Angelidaki and Sanders, 2004; Pham et

al, 2013), as it produced generally higher CH₄ concentrations (68%) compared to the GC (64.94%) (Pham et al, 2013).

Figure 11: Bio-methane potential test using liquid replacement method

BMP test for HOW as the feedstock can be determined using liquid replacement method LRM as illustrated in Figure 11, particularly the volumetric BMP method (Himanshu *et al*). A known amount of HOW with water added according to the ratio 1:1 was transferred into a 1L erlenmeyer flask. The flask was tightly sealed with air tight rubber stopper and A-grade super glue applied to ensure hermetic nature. Outlet of the flask was interconnected via capillary tube to another similar flask partly filled with water and stationed in an inclined position,

with its outlet angle of repose to a graduated cylinder to measure the water displaced by biogas concentration pressure in the flask head space.

3.3.2 *Sampling and quantifying organic waste resources*

Daily generation of HOW waste quantities of the participating household as well as their dietary intake was noted and reported by the members themselves throughout a time period of 28 days.

3.3.3 *Biogas theoretical yields*

Since HOW composition varies, substrate quality in terms of relative VS content, as well as process parameters and digester design, absolute biogas yield and methane content vary considerably. A review which considered many different biogas production experiment set-ups using both source-sorted and mechanically sorted OFMSW samples as substrate, and temperature

levels and various AD processes accordingly, reported that the results of methane yields differ approximately by a factor of ten (Campuzano and González-Martínez, 2016).

Nevertheless, a deductive approach can be incorporated to determine a reference value for the BMP, which can be used to estimate achievable volumes of biogas produced from HOW, based on literature review for potential biogas and methane yields. BMP values essentially account for TS content, relative VS content and volumes of methane formed per unit of VS mass.

Mean values of nine experiments estimates of biogas potential yields that confer similar operational conditions in the context of this study during the human organic waste AD process were used. TS and relative VS content, and methane volume formed per unit of VS mass directly relates to the BMP value deduced (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Reported mean methane potential for human organic waste

The absolute biogas volume (V_{BG}) produced from human organic waste can be estimated, assuming a methane content of 55 % by volume, of which mass of feedstock (m_{OW}) in terms of TS and VS is central to this estimation. Based on findings as summarized in Table 3, the TS content (TS) and VS content (VS_{TS}) of human organic waste is conservatively assumed to be 25 % and 89 % respectively:

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{BG} &= (m_{OW} * TS * VS_{TS} * BMP) * \frac{1}{0.55} = m_{OW} * 0.25 \frac{\text{kg}_{TS}}{\text{kg}_{OW}} * 0.89 \frac{\text{kg}_{VS}}{\text{kg}_{TS}} * 483.4 \frac{\text{dm}^3}{\text{kg}_{VS}} * \frac{1}{0.55} \\
&= m_{OW} * 195.6 \frac{\text{dm}^3}{\text{kg}_{OW}}
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Basing on comparable calculations deduced from previous studies literature (Vögeli et al., 2014; Rios and Kaltschmitt, 2016), the assumed energy content of the biogas produced (E_{BG}) corresponds to 0.006 kWh/dm³ (at standard temperature and pressure (STP) i.e. gas pressure and temperature is 1 bar and 25 °C, respectively):

$$E_{Bg} = V_{Bg} * 0.006 \frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{dm}^3} = V_{Bg} * 21.6 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{dm}^3} \tag{2}$$

3.3.4 Cost benefit analysis

With estimated theoretical biogas volumes, economic aspects into determining the monetary aspects can be delineated. As pointed out by Whyte and Perry (2001) vital variables to consider for AD technology cost assessments relative to the system's life expectancy on the site involves costs related to (i) starting capital, (ii) operational and maintenance and (iii) revenues and monetary savings. According to Perez et al., starting capital is a necessity in order to potentially implement and establish simple biogas production unit for research purposes, as well as operational expenses estimated to capture financial aspects relevant to real-life scenarios.

Limited by short periods of payback regarding minimal costs of investments attracts nil interest rates. As compared with similar AD designs (Ferrer et al., 2011; Vögeli et al., 2014; Pérez et al., 2014) the assumed life span proposed for ADT facility is 15 - 20 years. Assigning timing dimensions for operational costs, revenues and savings depends entirely on the frequency and mass of feedstock added to the system on a weekly, monthly and yearly basis accordingly with acquisition of spare parts and maintenance costs.

A comprehensive approach to economic cost analysis for domestic biogas production system adopted from Ali et al. (2019) to deduce payback period (PP) for the proposed OSS ADT system at Speedway village incorporates relevant aspects emphasized by Whyte and Perry (2001).

$$\text{Payback period (PP)} = \frac{\text{Investment required}}{\text{Annual cash flow}} = \frac{SCC+CIC}{R-OM} \quad (3)$$

- **SCC - ADT set-up components costs**

Retail prices in local shops of each component (*i*) according to dimension and number of items (*n*)

$$SCC = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{component} \quad (3.1)$$

- **CIC – construction and installation costs**

Labour costs associated with working hours (n_{CIC}) and local wages (per hour) (w_{CIC})

$$CIC = n_{CIC} * w_{CIC} \quad (3.2)$$

- R - revenues from product sale and savings through fuel and inorganic fertilizer replacement

S - savings through fuel replacement

Biogas produced promotes a savings (S_{ADD}) culture via conventional heating fuel i.e. biomass replacement, based on biomass acquisition prices (P_{LPG}) and replaced volumes (V_{BM}) in a year.¹

$$S_{ADD} = P_{LPG} * V_{LPG} * \frac{1}{\text{year}} \quad (3.3)$$

$$V_{LPG} = V_{BG} * \frac{1 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ BM}}{1,350 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ BG}}$$

Additional savings (S_{LF}) are achieved through substituting HOW solid fertilizer with inorganic fertilizer purchased from hardware stores, based on fertilizer prices for acquisition (P_F).

$$S_{LF} = P_F * \frac{1}{\text{year}}$$

$$R = S_{ADD} + S_{LF} \quad (3.4)$$

¹ One liter (dm³) of pressurized LPG (propane) as stored in a conventional gas bottle expands to 270 dm³ under normal conditions (i.e. 15 °C and 1 bar air pressure) (BOC, 2019). This in turn corresponds to 1350 dm³ of biogas, as the energy content per unit of volume of LPG compared to biogas is five times higher under normal conditions (Vögeli et al., 2014).

- **COM - costs for operation and maintenance during the lifespan of the biogas unit**

Operation costs include is limited to expenditures in the form of water demands for toilet flushing feedstock (E_W), and electricity (E_{El}) to run a gas compressor. Maintenance costs include necessary replacement of set-up components when the lifespan of the component is lower than the expected lifespan of the whole biogas unit, according to retail prices of replaced items (i). Additional labor time for regular maintenance checks and monitoring is considered (n_M). Regular tests in laboratories (LAB) to analyze nutrient content and identify contamination levels in the solid fertilizer are advised and considered in the calculation, based on testing costs in relevant institutes.

$$COM = (E_W + E_{El} + n_M + SUCi + \sum LABi) * \frac{1}{year} \quad (3.5)$$

The outlined cost assessment does not account for logistics associated with the distribution of the AD products to the end users as biogas will be used on-site and local farmers are expected to pick up the liquid digestate at the production site themselves. Following the idea of a sensitivity analyses, parameters in the cost estimations will be subject to variation in order to disclose effects on the payback period.

3.3.5 *Determining digester size*

For a suitable OSS system in PNG, wet AD digestion in a plug-flow digester model is appropriate for a finally proposed ‘domestic’ OSS facility in Speedway village. Justifications pertaining to the choice of the digester design will be discussed in the next chapter.

The size of the plug-flow digester as suggested by Rakotojaona (2013) is determined predominantly by the quantity or volume of feedstock added daily; the organic loading rate (OLR) and the storage space within the digester. OLR refers to the substrate quantity fed into the digester volume respective to time i.e. kg substrate (VS)/ m³ reactor/day. OLR directly influence the hydraulic retention time (HRT) i.e. the average time taken for the substrate to flow within the digester prior to being discharged, dictating how long it is subject to bacterial degradation

(Rakotojaona (2013) and Vögeli et al, 2014). HRT affects the operational temperature within the AD system. Volume of feedstock added comprise of volume of both the organic waste (V_{ow}) and water for dilution (V_w). Since the onsite ADT uses a semi-continuous process approach where feedstocks are added on a daily basis, (2014) further suggested that a suitable digester should have the ‘active’ slurry of 75 % of the total digester volume, with head space (i.e. remaining 25%) reserved for storage of biogas produce. Hence, the volume of a fixed-dome digester (V_D) can be determined as follows (Rakotojaona, 2013):

$$V_D = \frac{OLR*(V_{ow}+V_w)}{0.75} \quad (4)$$

3.3.6 Mass balance

To achieve a spontaneous AD process with special regard to the digester size determined (3), volume of the active slurry subject to digestion should be maintained in the digester. Hence, when feedstock is periodically added, liquid digestate of equal amount is displaced from the digester. Volume of digested slurry decrease as biogas formed due to break down of organic matter is continuously withdrawn. The loss is accounted with continuous addition of feedstock to the digester. Deublein and Steinhauser (2011) reported a reference value of biogas density of 1.2 kg/m³ that can be estimation for mass loss through biogas withdrawal from the digester (m_{BG}). However, methane content from the exact biogas composition dictates the biogas densities.

$$m_{BG} = V_{BG} * 1.2 \frac{kg}{m^3} \quad (5)$$

3.4 Preferred anaerobic toilet digester design

This study aims to provide a domestic onsite sanitation (OSS) system in the form of a domestic toilet integrating an anaerobic digester (AD) using affordable and accessible materials. Prior to that, various designs were proposed and critically examined (*see Results and Discussion*) to select a suitable design that fits the contemporary lifestyle and context for PNG.

The structural composition of the OSS ADT includes, a primary and secondary digester tanks that contains slurry as the main component, and the treatment tank. Digester tanks should be watertight and hermetic to create anaerobic conditions, including an inlet mechanism for feeding feedstocks, as well as an outlet for biogas and digestate extraction. Anaerobic digesters are diversely modified e.g. dry vs. wet digester, batch vs. continuous, one-stage vs. two-stage, etc., Nizami & Murphy (2010). In low-income regions, digesters reflect rural economic status, hence, are simpler than industrial solutions and so are called domestic digesters (Bond & Templeton, 2011). Generally domestic bio digesters are smaller than industrial digesters and are either onsite-constructed or prefabricated with different materials, as brick, concrete, and plastics.

Since the target is peri-urban centres, slums and rural areas, simplicity of OSS ADT in terms of the system assembly, user friendly, affordability and minimal maintenance are of primary importance even if the system is less efficient. Further still, the reuse of existing materials, e.g., pipes, tanks, etc. is acknowledged.

The anaerobic digestion process will be studied in prototype digester to develop an appropriate technology for the production of biogas from the human waste from rural and peri-urban settings, as illustrated in the diagram below.

3.4.1 Anaerobic digester system gas leakage test

To accord confidence to the ADT technology developed and to achieve the objective of an oxygen-free system, the air leakage test was performed using compressed air. The air was pumped into the system (b) and a pressure gauge (a) was inserted between the compressor and ADT system to detect air leakage by applying soap foam on specific joints and conjunctions.

(a)

(b)

Figure 13: Gas leakage test

3.5 Biogas purification, compression and bottling unit

To further promote the concept and encourage its acceptance locally, the study incorporates:

1. Design and establishment of biogas purification, compression and bottling unit
2. Conducting of various tests;
 - Carbon dioxide test i.e. quantity of carbon dioxide in biogas
 - Water acidity test to determine the pH of the system
 - Methane purity test, which in turn is determined by water boiling test i.e. heating equal volume of water to its boiling point while using raw and purified biogas with reference to time.

Experiments and analysis were limited, and monitoring and evaluations were conducted on a trial and error approach chiefly due to unavailability of Gas Analyzer, a standard measuring device which is required to verifying the results obtained. Measurements deduced were estimated based on evaluation of amount of carbon dioxide available in the biogas through the water acidity and water boiling tests.

3.5.1 Biogas purification unit

Water scrubbing is a conventional purification process whereby compounds or mixtures are physically separated by dissolution in water and is commonly used due to high availability, low cost, and low toxicity. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) are 26 and 75 times, respectively, more soluble and preferentially dissolve in water due to their high partial pressure as compared to methane (CH₄). Biogas scrubbing and storage unit designed constitute two components: scrubbing and storage sections. Figure 14 shows the schematics of the process flow of biogas treatment and storage.

Figure 14: Schematics of biogas purification, compression and storage unit

Complete elimination of H_2S selectively can be achieved by water scrubbing due to its higher solubility in water than CO_2 . However, the desorbed H_2S can result in fugitive irritating and unpleasant emissions. Hence, a pre-removal of H_2S prior to water scrubbing is more convenient.

Biogas purification unit comprise of three sections: hydrogen sulphide (H_2S) removal section, carbon dioxide (CO_2) removal section, and moisture entrapment and removal section. These three sections interlinked with capillary tubes form the basis of the purification process. Biogas purification is achieved by allowing raw biogas to pass through ferrous oxide (steel wool), then into tap water and finally the undissolved component of the gas is passed through an anhydrous material known as silica gel. Hydrogen sulphide is eliminated as it reacts with steel wool, while carbon dioxide percentage is reduced by water and finally presence of water vapour is eliminated by silica gel. With more biogas produced due to continual anaerobic reactions, raw biogas pressure increases in the head space of the digester and permeate its way through pores of the steel wool eliminating hydrogen sulphide as ferrous sulphide (FeS) as it proceeds to the water scrubbing unit. After H_2S removal, raw biogas flows into the water scrubber compartment wherein CO_2 dissolve in water to produce carbonic acid (H_2CO_3), a very weak acid.

Figure 15: Biogas scrubbing unit

Measuring pH of out-going water from scrubbing unit will serve to determine the water acidity, hence, indicating if scrubbing process objective is achieved. The effluent from water scrubbing process has high carbon dioxide concentration in the form of carbonic acid (H_2CO_3), while consequently highly concentrated methane gas departs the scrubbing unit. The treated biogas (methane) collected atop of the scrubber unit also has some water vapours which can lead to corrosion. Further purification of biogas was achieved using silica gel, an anhydrous substance that has very high affinity to moisture absorption.

3.5.2 *Biogas compression and storage*

As is always the issue with gaseous products, a safe and convenient storage of biogas is essential. The critical temperature and pressure of biogas are $-82.5^{\circ}C$ and 47.5bar respectively; thus, it is not practical to liquefy biogas at ambient temperature. Compressing biogas consequently improves storage requirements and reduces associated risks, offers increased energy content and provides sufficient pressure to counteract the resistance of the gas to flow freely. Conventionally preferred options for biogas storage that accommodate up to 200bar are propane tanks and commercial LPG gas cylinders. Demirbas *et al* (2006) pointed out that storage options and facilities vary based on the end-use biogas application (e.g. domestic cooking, electricity).

Biogas compression and storage unit comprise of three components;

- i. Compressor – a hermetically (sealed) reciprocating mode compressor specifically with hydrocarbon refrigerant, a vital component in commercial refrigerators.
- ii. Pressure gauge – to measure and monitor gas pressure at various intervals of compression.
- iii. LPG cylinder – for gas storage at higher pressure during and after compression

Figure 16: Biogas compression and bottling unit

Since biogas is not typically produced especially in quantity at the required time, to serve and satisfy the intended load/purpose, compression and storage is equally essential to offset variations in biogas supply and consumption. The storage unit in this regard also serves as a reservoir to ensure downstream equipment operates at without fluctuations at a constant pressure.

3.5.3 Treatment tank

Since the system uses a semi-continuous flow approach to add feedstock, as feedstock is dependent of human waste generation rate (see Table 2), biogas production will be consistent. However, overtime undigested cellulose mounds from human waste accumulates and eventually form

sediments, attesting to disparity in settling rates. These coarse particles settled individually, i.e. discrete particle settling, at rates reasonably estimated by stokes law;

$$V_s = \frac{gd^2(\rho_s - \rho_w)}{18\mu}$$

Where v_s = settling velocity (ms^{-1}), g = gravitational constant (9.81ms^{-2}), d = particle diameter (m), ρ_s = particle density (kgm^{-3}), ρ_w = water density (kgm^{-3}), and μ = dynamic viscosity (kgm^{-3}).

This formulation is assumed for spherical particles and laminar flow conditions around the particles during settling rates of 0.4 to 4000 mmsec^{-1} , which are reasonable estimates for human faecal waste particulate matter, as it not only settles rapidly within the digester, but to a relatively uniform density between 1400 to 1800 kgm^{-3} (Hayes et.al). The sedimentation accumulated in the digester can be flushed out to the treatment tank to create room for new feedstock. The treatment tank comprises of geotextile bag (geobag), a prominent and distinguished feature which is used for sediment management (Hayes et.al) is responsible for the treatment mechanism. For undigested celluloses that are mostly fines and coarse particles will remain proximate the inlet and settle to a natural angle of repose. Fine sediments will remain as suspension as slurry negotiate to permeate through geobag. Zone settling as a means of clarification will occur as long as surface overflow rate (SOR) is less than (or equal to) the zones settling velocity. SOR is defined as;

$$\text{SOR} = \frac{Q}{A_s}$$

Where SOR = surface overflow rate (ms^{-1}), Q = inflow rate (m^3s^{-1}), and A_s = horizontal area of the geobag (m^2). Most geobags form an elliptical shape with the horizontal axis longer than the vertical axis.

Hence, incorporating dewatering pre-treatment is necessary in order to maximize the efficacy of the desired aerobic degradation pathways. Since the solid faecal matter takes up to 20 days to decompose into richly fertile black organic material, it is safe for direct farming applications. Without the presence of water, there is no reaction and formation of unpleasant odour. The solid component breaks down within 15 days during sunny days, and can take up to 28 days during wet seasons.

3.5.4 *Biogas purification quality control:*

1. Acidity Test – was used to test for pH of:
 - water sample after scrubbing to verify the absorption of CO₂
 - effluent after treatment process
 - active slurry in digesters
2. CO₂ Test – was conducted using either (1) or lime water – Ca (OH)₂. With the latter, the lime water will turn milky due to the formation of CaCO₃, indicating the presence of CO₂.

3. H₂S Test – conducted using KOH.

4. Methane purity tests – 1L of tap water was heated using biogas before purification process, and after purification process relative to time to verify the efficacy of their performance.

3.6 **Qualitative assessment**

To facilitate early success of a proposed project by creating benefits in the long-term anchors on how the local community view, acknowledge and embrace the underlying concepts and principles (Schweizer-Ries, 2010; Eswarlal et al., 2014; Vögeli et al., 2014; Heaslip et al., 2016). Pivotal to success is the communication during initial planning phase and long-term acceptance of OSS facility after project implementation. Communicative tools such as questionnaire surveys and interviews are used to assess these social aspects.

3.6.1 *Identifying stakeholders*

To assess the project feasibility in a holistic manner it is of absolute importance to identify interested collaborators that are either affected by or can have dominant influence when it comes

to decision making and project implementation. Varvasovszky (2000) stressed that stakeholders can be individuals and or organizations, as well as collaborators of such or different networking partners. Analyses, either in a quantitative or qualitative approach to ascertain possible influential appropriate stakeholders with keen interest to the issue at hand have both advantages and drawbacks. A common and effective approach is interview with potential stakeholders (Varvasovszky, 2000)

Lohri et al. (2013) proposed as listed the relevant shareholders in developing countries that may potentially have interests in biogas production using organic waste; whose influence can dictate the success of the project implementation:

- Governmental authorities
- Legislator and enforcement agencies
- Funding agency
- Waste generators
- Design and installation experts
- Future operation & maintenance staff
- National and international NGOs
- Research institutions
- End-users of AD products
- Site residents

3.6.2. Approaching stakeholders

Considering the context of biogas production by biological treatment of human organic waste via OSS ADT system, perceptions and expectations of locals relative to renewable energy in general in the research area were explored using survey questionnaire. Formulated questions were adapted from question design principles proposed by Iarossi (2006), where interview questions should be (i) simple, (ii) brief, (iii) objective and (iv) specific. Appendix E contain the sample of the questionnaire.

Communication with stakeholders and subsequent questionnaire survey are pivotal for a final proposal of an OSS ADT system for biogas production.

4.0 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Theoretical feasibility

This study proposed and discussed various “domestic” OSS designs that incorporate AD process to produce biogas and organic fertilizer as the main by-products in the process of treating human wastes. A preferential design is one which take into consideration all the necessary characters of a developing country, particularly the case of PNG with special regard to the climatic conditions, economic status, lifestyle, etc. A prototype design of OSS facility with relatively simple, cost effective and environmentally friendly features that suit PNG context was then developed and trialled in the field. The OSS facility will be referred to in the following discussion as anaerobic digester toilet (ADT).

4.1.1 Proposed designs for anaerobic digester toilet system

Figure 17: Scheme of ADT sketch design # 1 (Not drawn to scale)

The initial sketch of the proposed design of on-site ADT system has four major components as illustrated in Figure 17, namely: (1) Feedstock inlet, (2) Digestion tank, (3) Purification and storage

unit, and (4) Treatment unit. as summarized in Table 10. The treatment unit beside all other components will be embedded.

Figure 18: ADT sketch design # 2: *Not drawn to scale*

ADT design sketch # 2 has all components proposed similar to *design #1*, except that the entire system is underground, purposefully to ensure user convenience; as well as changes to the feedstock inlet which uses siphon effects (see Table 10).

Figure 19: ADT sketch design # 3: *Not drawn to scale*

This particular design (Figure 19) seeks to integrate all the components into a single unit to encourage ease in using and accessing the facility, as well as maintenance and monitoring of the system. However, the design is uncapacious considering biogas storage space within the digester.

4.1.2 Preferred ADT design# 4:

Figure 20: Preferred ADT design# 4 (Top view): *Not drawn to scale*

Figure 21: Preferred ADT design# 4 (Iso view): *Not drawn to scale*

4.1.3 Summary of proposed on-site ADT designs

Table 11: Summary of proposed on-site ADT designs

ADT Design #	Pros	Cons
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Produce biogas and fertilizer (nutrient enriched soil) as by products - Moderate cost - Minimal maintenance - Simple and easy to install 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not conducive as it requires much efforts to negotiate stairs and transfer of water and animal manure for co-digestion for increased biogas production - Opening and closing valves may not be effective in oxygen removal as well as minimize odour problems - Unsafe storage of biogas
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Produce biogas and fertilizer (nutrient enriched soil) as by products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expensive - Requires more efforts - ADT may collapse due to violent earthquake or faulty scaffolds/frames
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Produce biogas - Very low cost - Minimal maintenance - Simple and easy to install 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uncapacious for produced biogas storage - Unsustainable due to inability to remove undigested cellulose/sediments - Sediment build-up
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moderate cost - Produce biogas and fertilizer (nutrient enriched soil) as by products - Minimal maintenance - Simple and easy to install 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Excessive biogas build-up in the head space can force the feedstock out of the inlet pathway

4.2 ADT cost estimate

Main components and the application as sketched in Figure. 20 & 21, is further explained in the following sections are listed in Table 12, along with acquisition costs. With regards to the payback period of the proposed set-up, a base line scenario illustrates the case of continuous deployment of the production unit over a year, i.e. 52 weeks, saving K89 (selling price) per quarter of a year i.e. 3 months in replacement of solid fertilizer. Calculations show a payback period for the proposed set-up according to the base line scenario of 1-3 months and annual cashflow accounts for K1,032.00. Calculation details can be found in Appendix C.

Table 12: Cost estimation of proposed set-up

#	Component	Dimension/ Properties	Nr.	Price in shops	Availability and source
1	Self-made digester (Water tank)	100 dm ³	2	100 Kina	Gala, East Taraka, Lae
2	Pipe fittings and valves	-	5	135 Kina	Badili Hardware, Market, Lae
3	Compressor hoses	15 m	1	38 Kina	Neon Hardware, Market, Lae
4	Gas fittings and valves	-	5	75 Kina	Badili Hardware, Market, Lae
5	Gas fittings and valves	-	5	75 Kina	Badili Hardware, Market, Lae
6	Pressure gauge	250kPa	1	140 Kina	Bishop Brothers, Market, Lae
7	Gas stove	-	1	90 Kina	Hardware Haus, Market, Lae
8	Silica gel	500g	1	42 Kina	Pool shop, Voco- point, Lae
	Additional items for assembling (glue, silicon to seal cracks, thread tape, etc.)			95 Kina (estimated)	
SUM				790 Kina	

Changes of parameters in the cost calculation serve for a comparison to the base line scenario and effects on the payback period (*PP*), annual revenues (*R*) and cashflow (*R-OM*), which are listed in Table 13. Considered were the reduction of the operational time in one year down to 12 weeks, as well as omitting LPG replacement savings by the produced biogas for feedstock treatment. Applying those parameter changes simultaneously, i.e. so to say the ‘worst’ case, calculations show a payback period of little more than a year.

Table 13: Sensitivity analyses for cost estimation (Appendix C)

Parameter changed	Payback period (PP)	Revenues (R)	Cash flow (R-OM)
None (base line)	1.5 months	180 Kina	180 Kina
Deployment for 12 weeks	2 months	600 Kina	360 Kina
Price for inorganic fertilizer K90 per 20 kg	3 months	180 Kina	90 Kina
LPG savings not considered	2 months	600 Kina	360 Kina

4.3 ADT design and construction

With respect to the design features and the pros and cons associated with special regard to PNGs context, *Design 4* ticks all the check lists. It was then explored, fabricated and installed on-site at the research area (Figure 22). The OSS facility was designed for a family unit of at least ten members. The church pastor and his family of seven as the major voluntary participants suits the system capacity, with visitors to make up to the prescribed user capacity. With special considerations beginning with configuration in Figure 17, the two-tank as in primary and secondary pattern is chosen, as in the plug-flow digester, due to its simplicity and reliability than the fixed-dome digester, which uses masonry structures. The ADTS has primary and secondary digestion tanks connected to the toilet pan via 100 mm PVC pipes, wherein the human waste, considered as the feedstock is transported to the digesters (Figure 20, 21 and 22).

The digestors are where the biological reactions occur to produce biogas occur. Thus, the vessel was carefully constructed, with gas sealant applied to prevent oxygen from entering, and finally gas leakage test was conducted using air compressor and a pressure gauge to verify the hermeticity of the digesters.

Figure 22: ADT constructed on-site (a) Inside toilet view (b) Front view (b) Back view

The excess slurry from primary digester is allowed to overflow into the secondary digester. This allows bubbles and scums formed due to rapid biological reactions in instances of excess added feedstock to propagate to secondary tank. The inlet route of the primary digester is located at the lower face of the container to prevent avenues for oxygen to enter. A valve is attached to the inlet, which is opened to perform flush-out of undigested cellulose or solid residues in the digester after specified duration of time intervals. This is a vital mechanism incorporated into the design for maintenance and sustainability purposes, hence, extending the life of the system. The amount of digestate that is discharged daily, as well as the approximate volume of the digester is shown in Figure 23. The effluent and undigested cellulose flushed out of the digesters are directed to the treatment tank where the predominant treatment is solid-liquid separation. This is achieved with the aid of geobag (*see* Figure 21), a geo-synthetic material perfectly suited for dewatering purposes. Anaerobic process itself disinfects approximately 95% of the pathogens, while the rest are entrapped in the geobag and further destroyed under continual natural process of composting,

i.e. after solid-liquid separation. Collected effluent was sampled and analysed a laboratory to confirm efficacy of the treatment process prior to discharge into the surrounding.

Figure 23: Summary of amount of feedstock added against digester volume

In order to mitigate ammonia accumulation and its toxicity impacts to the AD system, urine separation was encouraged.

4.4 Practical feasibility

4.4.1 Laboratory analysis and characterisation of human faeces

A total of ten samples reflecting common dietary intakes in rural and peri-urban settings in PNG was analysed. As expected, the median faeces generated was 250 g/cap/day wet mass and 62 g/cap/day dry mass, which implied that the dietary intake is rich in fibre. Consequently, high fibre intake also results in higher solid contents, both TS (49 g/cap/day) and VS (91% of TS i.e. 44.59 g/cap/day) due to high content of indigestible fibre, as compared to that of developed countries (Table 14). Mean value for COD determined was 80 g/cap/day. On the other hand, mean nitrogen value from faeces was 1.2 g/cap/day while that of urine was 7 g/cap/day, which is slightly lower when compared with that of the developed countries. These nitrogen values are mainly derived from plant proteins, which are common diets in low income countries, as well as less animal protein intake.

Table 14: Summary table of human faeces and urine characteristics analysed

Key design criteria	Median value
<i>Faeces</i>	
Faecal wet weight (g/cap/day)	250
Faecal dry weight (g/cap/day)	62
Total solids (%)	49
VS (% of TS)	91
COD (g/cap/day)	68
Nitrogen (g/cap/day)	1.2
pH	6.8
<i>Urine</i>	
Urine wet weight (L/cap/day)	1.4
Urine dry weight (g/cap/day)	59

Nitrogen (g/cap/day)	7
pH	6.3

4.4.2 Biogas actual yield

Biogas produced from the OSS ADTS was observed to be low when only human organic waste (HOW) was considered as the main feedstock, which accordingly is due to low solid content in HOW. When animal manure (AM) i.e. chicken manure was co-digested with HOW, biogas produced steadily increased as can be delineated in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Comparison of biogas produced from human organic waste (HOW) and HOW+ chicken manure (HOW+AM)

The volume of methane (after purification of the produced biogas) was also proved to increase as the feedstock increase.

4.5 Purification of biogas

4.5.1 Hydrogen sulphide removal

Hydrogen sulphide (H_2S) was reduced to black iron sulphide (FeS) using steel wool. Figure 4 demonstrated what happened before and after using steel wool in the scrubbing process.

a) Steel wool prior to scrubbing

b) Steel wool after scrubbing

Figure 25: Hydrogen sulphide removal

4.5.2 Water vapour removal

During elimination of water vapour, blue silica gel changed to pink, indicating presence of water after moisture absorption from the biogas.

a) Silica gel before moisture removal

b) Silica gel after moisture removal

Figure 26: Moisture absorbent

Different approaches can be taken to purify gas and test for its purity, for instance using common tests such as water boiling test to test for biogas purity. Result obtained via this method shows that biogas concentration is higher in purified biogas, than in raw biogas as summarized below;

Table 15: Purity of raw and purified biogas

Raw biogas	Purified biogas
68 ± 2.52 %	90 ± 1.53 %

4.5.3 Effect of purification on heating value

Since appropriate instrument such as gas analyser was unavailable, effects of purified and raw biogas against cooking time and calorific value was investigated using 1 L of water to verify and confirm purification of biogas.

Table 16: Time taken to boil 1L of water

Energy Source	Time (minutes) taken to boil 1L of water
Raw biogas	6.54 ± 0.04
Purified biogas	5.45 ± 0.02

Vividly, purified biogas has higher calorific heating value, thus, required less heating time than raw biogas. This demonstrates that methane is the predominantly gas that is responsible for the combustibility of biogas, whereas the other components of the mixture in biogas is considered of no use, harmful or toxic. Hence, raw biogas purification particularly for the removal of CO₂ is a necessity to improve its calorific value.

4.5.4 Water acidity test

To confirm CO₂ removal during the scrubbing process, acidic test is done on the water leaving the scrubbing unit. The pH value of water before and after the scrubbing process was 6.8 ± 0.12 and 4.7 ± 0.22 respectively. Basing on this observation, it was concluded that water scrubbing is effective to some extent in removal of CO₂.

4.5.5 Compression and storage

Finally, biogas (methane) was compressed into an LPG cylinder after the purification and drying processes. A hermetically sealed reciprocating compressor of dysfunctional refrigerant was used to compress purified gas up to an absolute pressure of 5 bars in total of approximately 12 minutes. Figure 9 depicts the volume of methane gas that can be compressed with a pressure of 5 bar using the hermetic reciprocating compressor.

Figure 27: Compressed and non-compressed methane gas

4.6 Local acceptance

The questionnaire survey conducted explored perceptions concerning contemporary OSS facilities as well as the associated health and environmental risks, including residential energy sources and demands. Willingness to participate in new technologies to embark on more environmentally friendly approach to managing HOW was also explored. Participants of the survey were mainly residents within Speedway village including interested church members.

Low acquisition price followed by continuous supply for energy have been perceived by the respondents as more important aspects than decentralized energy production and an environmentally friendly residential energy supply as shown in Figure 28. As depicted in Figure 29, survey results further revealed that the majority of locals are not content with the contemporary approach to human waste management, although they have limited to no knowledge of the negative implications of improper management of human waste to human health and the environment. Nonetheless, they strongly pushed for renewable energy sources as the way forward.

Figure 28: Survey results question 3

Figure 29: Survey results question 1, 2 and 4

The survey also revealed that participants are also aware of value of organic waste at large. This is a positive signal that alternate use of human waste may also be accorded consideration to certain

extent, given the potential benefits are fully understood and appreciated. As seen in Figure 30, many participants strongly support biogas production

Figure 30: Survey results question 5, 6 and 7

However, although majority of the respondents welcome the idea of biogas production from human faeces and are willing to participate in using OSS ADT technology, a good number oppose the concept due to negative misconceptions pertaining to human faeces.

Importance of recovery from wastes have being sporadically signalled by the survey participants, as well as a need for rigorous educational awareness and promotion of the technological concept is acknowledged and in order. Detailed data for the survey results can be found in Appendix E, along with the survey questionnaire.

4.7 Identifying and contacting stakeholders

Approaching representative of the health department in particularly the metropolitan water, sanitation and hygiene (WaSH) coordinator early on in the Thesis work has been advantageous, as insights to the pressing health issues relating to faecal mismanagement were discussed and the need for innovative technologies to tackle these issues were acknowledged. This stakeholder, as well as few other relevant stakeholders such as government department and sectoral head were approached for collaborations (see Appendix A). The beginning seemed promising as interests

were sparked as the stakeholders begin to grasp the importance of OSS ADT technological concept and coming to terms with its relevance to improving human health and the environment.

Focus was then diverted to a local church community at Speedway village, approaching the church pastor who also showed interest in project participation to the field work. The church's head pastor and administrator directly contacted me for project collaboration and voluntary participation for proto-type trial after the motives and objectives of the field study were explained.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This study eloquently addressed the waste and HW management and sanitation topics for low-income countries and within rural areas, slums and settlements. Literacy barriers, as well as various misconceptions surrounding HOW as a feedstock for biogas production among residents is a concerning challenge regarding data collection while conducting field work. However, support granted by local stakeholders and the simplicity of the ADT design and methods applied allowed for smooth investigations.

This study explored that OSS ADTS is a suitable treatment for HOW in Speedway village and can be replicated in other parts of PNG, fostering benefits in the light of Sustainable Development.

In conclusion:

- The OSS ADTS design choice and application was motivated for replicability and wider applicability in other settings with similar conditions for further research and developments.
- The domestic OSS ADTS designed for HOW management and valorisation to produce biogas and organic fertilizer is a win-win solution for safe disposal of HOW as well as alternate sustainable fuel and fertilizer for local domestic uses, particularly within emerging and marginalised contexts.
- To increase the efficacy of the ADTS, co-digestion especially with animal manure is essential as it boost methane production, as well as the increased solid content which accordingly increases the organic fertilizer yields.
- The applied methods for the purification, compression and storage systems proved to be very affordable and accessible, thus, suits PNG context. Further still, purifying biogas increases the calorific value, whereas compression increases the mobility and encourages user convenience.
- Generally, the strategies and methods applied in this study are simple and cost-effective, and can be replicated in other places, not limited to Papua New Guinea.

- An MOU between DCE Unitech & P.A.W.A. Ministry is in progress (Appendix G) for further collaboration with special regard to OSS AD facility monitoring and evaluation for and future researches to improve on the system design and performances.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A

“Portable Anaerobic Bio-digester System (PABS) Concept Awareness and Funding Pursuit”

Meeting #1

Contact: Mr. Harold Abori – Goroka Town Authority Town Manager

Date: Tuesday 29-06-2021

Time: 9 – 9:30am

Dialogue:

- Made awareness on the PABS Concept Overview
- Highlighted the health, environment and socio-economic importance associated with the technology and the relevance to our locality context.
- Inquired for appropriate technical personnel for further discussions and deliberations

Output:

- Meeting with GTA Engineer arranged

Note:

Goroka Town Authority (GTA) is a statutory body appointed by Eastern Highlands Provincial Government to manage the daily operations and affairs of Goroka town. Municipal waste management, and other major facilities such as water, waste water treatment facility, and all the activities associated with the welfares of the inhabitants of Goroka Town are the sole responsibility of the GTA.

Meeting #2

Contact: GTA Engineer

Date: Thursday 01-07-2021

Time: 11 – 12 noon

Dialogue:

- Made awareness on the PABS Concept Overview
- Highlighted the health, environment and socio-economic importance associated with the technology and the relevance to our locality context
- Inquired of personnel's perspective on the concept, and possibility for funding from GTA or possible donors such as EHP Provincial Government for immediate implementation.

Output:

- GTA Engineer supports the concept as “emerging concept that has immense potential”. Further elaboration was given on the production of biogas component of the concept.
- Was advised to finalize the concept and concept design and hopefully come up with submission to be addressed to the Town Manager

Meeting #3

Contact: Mr. Martin Moses – EHPHA WASH Coordinator

Date: Thursday 08-07-2021

Time: 2 – 3pm

Dialogue:

- Made awareness on the PABS Concept Overview
- Highlighted the health, environment and socio-economic importance associated with the technology and the relevance to our locality context
- Inquired of personnel's perspective on the concept, and possibility to sort funding from EHPHA or Donor Agencies such as UN, UNICEF etc. for immediate implementation

Output:

- Concept was embraced and praised as “an innovative means to mitigate health and environmental issues associated with improper management of human wastes (and organic wastes) management in our peri-urban and rural areas, paving way for sustainable developments in terms of alternate energy source and fertilizer synthesis”.
- Assured support for conference and or seminar presentations for further concept awareness and marketing.

Limitations with acceptance of concept:

1. Complacent attributes gestured by higher authorities; lack of innovation and creative thinking
2. Prefabricated designs and technologies provided by Donors for our consumptions

Friday 16.07.2021 @ 1:30 – 2pm

Inquired at KKKinston Head Office, Milford Street – Lae

Contact: Technical Rep

Dialogue:

- Possibility to engage R&D
- Possibility to consider my design for PABS production

Output:

- Company ceased R&D a few years ago
- Market has to be secured before production, there has to be a demand for the product. (They’d manufacture in quantity and so require stable demand and supply).

Appendix B

Recorded data on participants using the OSS ADTS proto-type; human organic waste generation rate; volume of HOW and animal manure used, as well as the water ratio used for the digestion process; to determine the digester volume

No. people	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
OLR (kg/L/day)	0.25	0.5	0.75	1	1.25	1.5	1.75	2	2.25	2.5
m_{how} (kg)	0.25	0.5	0.75	1	1.25	1.5	1.75	2	2.25	2.5
V_w (dm³)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
m_{how} + V_w	1.25	2.5	3.75	5	6.25	7.5	8.75	10	11.25	12.5
Vol. Digester (dm³)	0.42	1.67	3.75	6.67	10.42	15.00	20.42	26.67	33.75	41.67
m_{ahow} (kg)	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20
V_{ahow}+V_w	4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36	40
Vol. Digester (dm³)	1.33	5.33	12.00	21.33	33.33	48.00	65.33	85.33	108.00	133.33

m_{how} = mass of human organic waste; V_w = Vol. water used; m_{ahow} = combined mass of animal manure and human organic waste

V_{bg} (how) dm³	48.9	97.8	146.7	195.6	244.5	293.4	342.3	391.2	440.1	489
V_{bg} (how) (m³)	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.24	0.29	0.34	0.39	0.44	0.49
V_{bg} (ahow) dm³	391.2	782.4	1173.6	1564.8	1956	2347.2	2738.4	3129.6	3520.8	3912
V_{bg} (ahow) (m³)	0.39	0.78	1.17	1.56	1.96	2.35	2.74	3.13	3.52	3.91
V_{methane} (m³)	0.25	0.51	0.76	1.02	1.27	1.53	1.78	2.03	2.29	2.54

V_{bg} (how) = Vol. of biogas from human organic waste; V_{bg} (ahow) = Vol. of biogas from animal manure and human organic waste; V_{methane} = Vol. of methane gas

Appendix C

Calculations

Biogas yields, LPG replacement and mass loss

Daily biogas yields from daily quantities of HOW 2 kg:

$$m_{OW} = 2 \text{ kg}$$

$$V_{BG} = m_{OW} * 195.6 \frac{dm^3}{kg_{OW}} = 2 * 195.6 \frac{dm^3}{kg_{OW}} = 391.2 dm^3$$

Weekly LPG replacement through daily biogas yields on seven days a week:

$$V_{LPG} = V_{BG} * \frac{1 dm^3_{BM}}{1,350 dm^3_{BG}} * 7 = 391.2 dm^3_{BG} * \frac{1 dm^3_{BM}}{1,350 dm^3_{BG}} * 7 = 2.02 dm^3_{LPG}$$

Weekly savings through LPG replacement with biogas yields

$$S_{ADD} = P_{LPG} * V_{LPG} = 25 * \frac{K}{16.5 dm^3_{LPG}} * 2.02 dm^3_{LPG} = K3.07 \quad (E 3.6)$$

Appendix D

Temp. °C	1000	2000	3000	4000	5000	6000	7000	8000	9000	10000
Pressure_5bar	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Initial Vol. (dm³)	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Initial Vol. (m³)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Vol. Compressed dm³	4521	9042	13563	18083	22604	27125	31646	36167	40688	45208
Vol. Compressed (m³)	4.52	9.04	13.56	18.08	22.60	27.13	31.65	36.17	40.69	45.21

Appendix E

Survey questionnaire

1) How do you view the current approach in which human waste is managed?

Please **tick** the box with your answer.

- okay need improvement I don't know
-

2) Are you aware of the health and environmental implications associated with improper management of human faeces?

Please **mark your answer with a tick** in the right box.

- Yes No I don't know

If yes, what are some of the implications?

.....
.....

3) How important to you are the following aspects of energy supply (e.g. gas for cooking, electricity.)?

Weigh each aspect between (1) **least important** and (10) **most important**.

- () low price () decentralized energy production
() no interruptions of the supply () environmentally friendly
() other (pls. specify):
-

4) Alternate energy sources such as solar, biofuels, hydropower, and wind are should play an important role for the energy supply in Speedway village and PNG rather than conventional energy sources like natural gas, coal or diesel.

Please **tick** the box with your answer.

- I agree I do not agree I don't know
-

5) Are organic wastes (kitchen waste, food leftovers) produced at your home of any significance to you?

Please **tick** the box with your answer.

- Yes No I don't know

If yes, what kind of value?

.....
.....

6) Human faeces are categorized as organic waste (similar to kitchen waste, food leftovers, yard debris, etc.). All organic material naturally breaks down to form a combustible gas, known as biogas. Biogas can be used for cooking, heating and power generation, if effectively applied. What remains after the break down process can be used as an organic fertilizer in farming.

Would you go for or against biogas production from human organic waste in Speedway village?

Please **tick** the box with your answer.

- Go for Against I don't know

If you go for or against, why?

.....
.....

7) Anaerobic Digester Toilet uses naturally occurring biological processes to treat human faeces to produce biogas and fertilizer as the by-products. Would you be willing to use this technology to encourage biogas production and simultaneously mitigate environment and health issues in Speedway?

Please **mark your answer with a cross** in the box.

- Yes No I don't know

Results of the survey questionnaire

Human faeces management

(60 participants)

1) *How do you view the current approach in which human faeces is managed?*

Answer	Nr. respondents	%
Okay	7	12%
Need improvement	42	70%
Don't know	9	15%
No answer	2	3%

Environment and health implications

(60 participants)

2) *Are you aware of the health and environmental implications associated with improper management of human faeces?*

(60 participants)

Answer	Nr. respondents	%
Yes	15	25%
No	35	58%
Don't know	7	12%
No answer	3	5%

Aspects of residential energy sources

(60 participants)

3) How important to you are the following aspects of energy supply (e.g. gas for cooking, electricity,)?

Please weigh each aspect between (1) least important and (10) most important.

Score	Average	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	No answer
low price	5	0	0	0	0	1	2	4	5	8	34	4
decentralized energy production	6	0	0	6	0	10	0	10	10	3	16	10
no interruptions of supply	6	2	3	1	3	10	2	2	8	4	23	5
environmentally friendly	7	4	1	1	0	0	0	3	3	7	46	13

Renewable energy in Speedway

(60 participating households)

4) Alternate energy sources such as solar, biofuels, hydropower, and wind are should play an important role for the energy supply in Speedway village and PNG rather than conventional energy sources like natural gas, coal or diesel.

Answer	Nr. respondents	%
Agree	51	85%
Disagree	3	5%
Don't know	5	8%
No answer	1	2%

Perception of organic household waste

(60 participating households)

5) Are organic wastes (kitchen waste, food leftovers) produced at your home of any significance to you?

Answer	Nr. respondents	%
No	14	23%
Yes	40	67%
Don't know	4	7%
No answer	2	3%

Attitude towards local biogas production in Speedway

(70 participating households)

6) Human faeces are categorized as organic waste (similar to kitchen waste, food leftovers, yard debris, etc.). All organic material naturally breaks down to form a combustible gas, known as biogas.

Biogas can be used for cooking, heating and power generation, if effectively applied. What remains after the break down process can be used as an organic fertilizer in farming.

Would you go for or against biogas production from human organic waste in Speedway village?

Answer	Nr. respondents	%
Oppose	5	8
Support	48	80
Don't know	7	12
No answer	0	0

Willingness to use Anaerobic Digester Toilet human faecal treatment for local biogas production at source

(70 participating households)

7) Anaerobic Digester Toilet uses naturally occurring biological processes to treat human faeces to produce biogas and fertilizer as the by-products. Would you be willing to use this technology to encourage biogas production and simultaneously mitigate environment and health issues in Speedway?

Answer	Nr. respondents	%
Yes	38	63
No	12	20
Don' know	6	10
No answer	4	7

Appendix F

Human excreta composition of ten test persons

	Unit	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<i>Faeces</i>											
Wet mass	(g/cap/day)	224	258	263	181	286	251	275	300	267	194
Dry mass	(g/cap/day)	58	63	65	41	71	63	70	75	68	46
Ash	(g/cap/day)	16	19	22	13	29	18	24	32	21	16
COD	(g/cap/day)	62	69	71	57	72	67	73	79	69	61
N	(g/cap/day)	1.1	1.3	1	0.8	2.1	1.2	1	1.3	1.6	0.7
pH	(g/cap/day)	6.8	6.7	6.9	6.8	6.7	6.7	6.8	6.9	6.9	6.8
<i>Urine</i>											
Wet mass	L/cap/day	1.4	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.7	1.5	1.2
Dry mass	(g/cap/day)	59	64	67	45	63	58	60	69	56	49
N	(g/cap/day)	6.6	6.8	7.2	5.6	7.5	7.0	7.1	9.5	6.9	5.8

Appendix F

Memorandum of Understanding (MOU)

Between the

**Department of Civil Engineering Papua New Guinea University of
Technology (DCE-Unitech)**

And the

P.A.W.A. Ministry Church Community – Speedway

1. Parties of MOU

Department of Civil Engineering-Papua New Guinea University of Technology (DCE-Unitech)

The Department of Civil Engineering is the oldest in the Papua New Guinea University of Technology (PNGUoT or known as Unitech) having been established with the University at its inception in 1965, first as the Institute of Technology and until its upgrade to the University status. The Department serves the Civil Engineering Industry in Papua New Guinea (PNG) and the Pacific through its graduates and also in the research and development work, consultancy services, and its community services. The Department of Civil Engineering offers both Undergraduate (one Bachelor's Degree only) and several Postgraduate (PG) programs. The Bachelor in Engineering (BE) program has been upgraded to Provisional accredited to Washington Accord thru Engineers Australia (<https://www.engineersaustralia.org.au/sites/default/files/2021-06/Web%20List%20-%20V43%20-%20210623.pdf>). The PG programs include: MPhil, MSc; and MEng, and PhD. Students for the PG programs include both Nationals and overseas candidates, the latest being from the Caribbean (MPhil, 2016). The MEng program have specializations in the following areas: Structural Engineering, Transportation Engineering, Geotechnical Engineering, Water Resources Engineering and Environmental Engineering.

The strategic areas of Unitech include the following:

1. To provide an International Standard in Research & Development, Technology and Knowledge Transfer, External Collaboration & Partnerships, Consulting Engineering, Commercial Testing and Community Services in the discipline of Civil Engineering in PNG and the South Pacific.

Key areas of work:

1. Coordinating with stakeholders to formulate policy and management methods of promoting cleaner production;
2. Being responsible for technical supervision and capacity building of domestic Onsite Sanitation (OSS) systems for local human waste management and cleaner production;
3. Providing training courses for national cleaner production auditors;
4. Providing other services for human waste management for instance, waste treatment and discharge, sampling and laboratory analysis and reporting, and environmental monitoring and evaluation.

Pentecostal Assemblies of The World Apostolic (P.A.W.A Ministry)

Pentecostal Assemblies of The World Apostolic also known as P.A.W.A. Ministry is a religious institution that promotes Jesus Christ and His Teachings. P.A.W.A. Ministry was established in 2015. Since its inception this Ministry was survived by Ps. Gilbert, his wife and children, and three other couples and their children, totaling to an initial population of almost 20. Fast forward seven years and today P.A.W.A. Ministry is one of the largest in Speedway village and also in Lae City with 400 plus population of church members, including children. The PNG P.A.W.A. Ministry is headed by Ps. Kelage Sine, a senior pastor and overseer. The Ministry has different sub ministries

within, such as song ministry, children's ministry, prayer ministry, welfare ministry, etc. P.A.W.A. Ministry also participates in local activities such as community service and outreach programme, to be a part of the community and to share the love of Jesus to others. As its values, P.A.W.A. Ministry promotes healthy lifestyle practices.

2. Scope of Cooperation

The DCE-Unitech represented by **Dr. Mirzi Betasolo** in her capacity as the Researcher Team Leader, and P.A.W.A. Ministry represented by **Ps. Kelaga Sine**, pastor in charge have agreed on the following MOU. The parties have mutually recognized the capacities of each other to promote the cooperation between Unitech Civil Engineering Department and P.A.W.A. Ministry within the framework of "Water, Sanitation and Hygiene, and Renewable Energy) Initiative" supported by the PNG University of Technology, Department of Civil Engineering in the following areas:

- Support for anaerobic digester toilet (ADT) for onsite sanitation (OSS) implementation.
- Acquiring equipment for human excreta collection, treatment and disposal, onsite monitoring, renewable energy, waste-water treatment, etc.
- E-Waste recovery systems. Knowledge, technology and implementation.
- Acquiring technology and support for monitoring, consulting and engineering for constructions of treatment plants, transport systems, energy systems, etc.
- Develop a cooperation program supporting technology and communication systems for human and animal waste management in local governments.
- Development cleaner production technology transfer and standardization.
- Promote healthy and sustainable lifestyle concept

3. Responsibilities

For the implementation of this MOU the signed parties will work closely as follows:

The **P.A.W.A. Ministry**, Pentecostal Assembly of God:

- Facilitate the site for project establishment and identified areas of cooperation within the program of "Water, Sanitation and Hygiene, and Renewable Energy) Initiative" supported by the PNG government and other relevant stakeholders
- Facilitate the field visit of DCE-Unitech and other interested stakeholders.
- Establish mutual understanding and corporation (E.g. Ensure safe keeping of OSS ADT facility and reliable recording of data)
- Facilitate the fund raising for identified areas of cooperation within relevant stakeholders
- Facilitate technical cooperation with local actors and health and relevant sectors

**Department of Civil Engineering-Papua New Guinea University of Technology
(DCE-Unitech):**

- Facilitate the project establishment and identified areas of cooperation within the program of "Water, Sanitation and Hygiene, and Renewable Energy) Initiative" supported by the PNG government and other relevant stakeholders
- Facilitate the fund raising for identified areas of cooperation within relevant stakeholders
- Facilitate of technical cooperation with specific thematic areas (e.g Onsite Sanitation and E-Waste recovery)
- Facilitate technical cooperation with local actors and health and relevant sectors
- Facilitate technology, knowledge and information transfer programs through research and development
- Facilitate the cooperation with P.A.W.A. Ministry to identifying the possible alternative in viewing human waste in terms of Resource Efficiency and Cleaner Production
- Facilitation of technical cooperation with areas of priorities
- Support of development of joint preparation of technical proposals on "Water, Sanitation and Hygiene, and Renewable Energy) Initiative" topics
- Facilitate of technology, knowledge and information transfer programs between DCE-Unitech and P.A.W.A. Ministry and relevant Stakeholders
- Undertake field visit to P.A.W.A. Ministry to gather relevant information for research and redevelopment of the OSS-ADT facility.

4. Monitoring and Evaluation of MOU

To ensure the effectiveness of this cooperation, a technical cooperation committee from representatives from CNCPC and DCE-Unitech will be formed for regular review of cooperation and meet either in China or PNG one per year if possible or via video conferences.

5. Duration of MOU

The duration of this MOU will be 2 years from the date of signature with possibility for extension based on mutual agreement

6. Signatures

Dr. Ora Renagi

Ps. Kelaga Sine

Vice Chancellor

Pastor in charge

Papua New Guinea University of Technology

Pentecostal Assemblies of The World Apostolic

Date:

Date:

Witnessed by:

Dr. Mirzi Betasolo

Mr. Unaro Yauo

Project Supervisor/Coordinator

Project-Thesis/Developer

Senior Lecturer – Civil Engineering Department

DCE, PNG University of Technology

Papua New Guinea University of Technology

Date:

Date: